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File outline

```

1 [00:00:00]
2
3 R: Ok, thank you. Let's see... How many, did you do, are you Computing Science or Artificial Intelligence?
4 S: Computing Science.
5 R: Ok, and which, did you pass the imperative programming? That was in...?
6 S: Yes, in C++.
7
8 [00:00:23]
9
10 R: Ok. So I wanna show you a piece of code and I'd like to ask you to read, yeah you have to describe the purpose of this
    code, so if this would be a function, what would you call the function? If you wanna sit a bit closer to be more
    comfortable, please.
11 [00:00:40]
12 [BEGIN TASK 34a]
13 S: I think that based on the for-loop, the function, it's eh, calculating the highest rain, the highest rainValue. So... I
    would give it a maximum rainValue.
14 [END TASK 34A]
15 [00:01:07]
16 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34A]
17 R: Ok, let's see, I have a... Ok, so the goal of the code, how would you call it? You can type there the maximum.
18 S: So the name of the function or the... Ok. Ehm... [types "MaximumRainValue"]
19
20 [00:01:44]
21
22 R: Ok. And if I would ask you to look at the program code, so that's the algorithm, how complex do you find it?
23 S: Ehm, not very complex.
24 R: Ok, on a scale from 0 is the simplest and 10 is the most complex?
25 S: I guess, zero.
26
27 [00:02:02]
28
29 R: Ok, good. Ok, there's a few concepts which you see here, for example, what do you see in row, line 4?
30 S: It's an... array of integers.
31 R: Yeah, exactly, so you have an array, and in 6, what happens in 6?
32 S: It's a... It's the first value in the array.
33 R: Ok. So you see that it's indexing a value, it has something to do with arrays and you said here this is a for each-loop.
    So there's a few concepts which are here, how hard do you find the, concepts that you... Ok, great.
34
35 [00:02:39]
36
37 R: All right, and was it clear what I wanted you to do?
38 S: Yes.
39 R: Ok, so that's very unclear, and 0 means it's clear... Ok, perfect. So, now the second one is also code-reading.
40 S: Ehm...
41 [END DISCUSS TASK 34A]
42 [00:03:02]
43 [BEGIN TASK 34B]
44 R: So what do you see?
45 S: So we have, we have again an array of values, of integers, we pick the first value in the array, ehm... and then we have
    a while, which I think it's an index, and then ehm... Oh, so it does the same thing, it's just that now we choose an index
    and we calculate it separately, we add one to it everytime we check an element.
46 R: Ok, and why do we do that?
47 S: Ehm... Just to go through the array.
48
49 [00:03:41]
50
51 R: Ok, yeah, yeah, good. All right, and what would you call the function?
52 S: Ehm... Well, I'd call it the same as the previous, but I don't know the difference, so...
53 R: Ok, what's the purpose of the code? What does it do?
54 S: The same purpose.
55 R: If that's the purpose, then you can call it the same. So if you can type it here...
56 S: [types "MaximumRainValue"]
57 [END TASK 34B]
58
59 [00:04:14]
60 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34B]
61 R: Ok. Now, again, if you look at the algorithm that you see there, is this easier or more difficult than the previous one?
62 S: The same.
63 R: And the concepts? So you had a while-loop, instead of a for-loop...
64 S: It's the same.
65 R: Ok, it didn't make any difference for you that it's a while-loop? No, ok.
66 S: Ehm... Yeah.
67 [END DISCUSS TASK 34B]
68 [00:04:45]
69 [BEGIN TASK 34C]
70 R: Ok. Another one.
71 S: Ehm... So we have the same array of integers, ehm... We have a count variable, and we go through the array with the,
    this time with a normal for-loop. And ehm, we count how many values are zero in the array. And I call this, ehm, countNull,
    I think.
72 R: Ok.
73 S: [types "CountNull"]
74 [END TASK 34C]
75 [00:05:38]
76 [BEGIN DISCUSS 34C]
77 R: And if you look at the code, the algorithm...?
78 S: It's pretty easy as well.
79 R: Is it any more difficult than the one you did before?
80 S: No, and the instructions were clear.
81 [END DISCUSS 34C]
82 [00:05:50]
83 [BEGIN COMPARE AND DISCUSS READING TASKS]
84 R: Ok. Now I have these three pieces of code we've just looked at, ehm, this was the first one with the for each-loop, this
    is the one with the while-loop, and this is the normal for. You said they all did generally the same thing, you had
    absolutely no problem looking at what it is, but I would like you to ask, if you look at these pieces of code, could you
    order them, in terms from hard to difficult?
85 S: Oh, ok. Ehm...
86 R: Ok. So the for each, you say, is the hardest?
87 S: Yeah just because sometimes, maybe in this case it's not as hard, but if I have an array of arrays, I usually make a
    mistake on what type of this variable is here, but...
88 R: So for a double array, it could become into a problem?
89 S: Yeah.

```

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You: S6 WHILE harder/dispersed/error prone than FOR Jan 10, 2024 1:51 PM • Edit

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You: S2 FOR understandable Jan 10, 2024 1:51 PM • Edit

90 R: Ok. And why do you find the while more complex than the normal for?
91 S: Just because it's more coded, more lines of code than this, so it's, you just need to know that you have to put the `++` in the right place.
92 R: Because here you don't have to do that?
93 S: No.
94 R: Because it's just automatically there. And more lines of code because here you have actually these three in one line. Ok. So I'm gonna put them like this, all right, perfect.
95
96 [00:07:32]
97
98 R: Now I'm going to ask you to write a piece of code. I'd like you to read the question.
99 [00:07:40]
100 [BEGIN TASK 81]
101 S: [silence for 15 seconds]
102 R: So, what is asked?
103 S: So we need to calculate the, how many times the maximum amount of rain fell, which is 76 in this case.
104
105 [00:08:06]
106
107 R: What are you gonna do, what's your plan?
108 S: Ehm... I want to do a for-loop through the array and, ehm, I'll have a maximum variable that takes the first, ehm, value, and then we go through the array and see which is a maximum first, and then another for-loop to, oh, no, we can do the same, with the same for-loop and everytime we find a different maximum value, we can preset the counter to 1. So... Counter to 1, and the int maximum equals to rainValues... zero. Ehm... Now we do the for-loop. Ehm, so we have an if, ehm, rainValues of i bigger than maximum... Ehm... we change the maximum to the new value. And we reset the count to 1. Ehm... else if... rainValues of i, eh, equals, equals to maximum, then we just increase the count with 1.
109 [END TASK 81]
110 [00:10:39]
111 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 81]
112 R: Ok. I'm gonna ask you not to run the code. Ehm, I'm not interested in syntax errors, so I just wanna know how you're doing this, and if you run the code, you're gonna get feedback, and that's not the goal of the research. Ok, ehm, good, I had a question. why did you, oh you started the i, you started the iterator with an `i = 1` [for int i =1:]. why?
113 S: Ehm, because we already have the first element, so we don't need to check it again.
114
115 [00:11:06]
116
117 R: Ok, perfect. All right, good, great. Let's see... The frequency of the maxima. Ok, if you look at your code, and compared to the things that we've done before, how difficult do you find the algorithm? Is it more complex, or how complex is it?
118 S: Ehm, I don't think it's more complex, but I just put the 1, I guess.
119 R: And why?
120 S: Ehm, well because, I mean, maybe, some people would just decide to first do the for-loop, to find out what the maximum is and then check how many times it is in there, but I, it's not that hard to combine the two if you know how to do the if and else.
121
122 [00:11:50]
123
124 R: Yeah, and you have to of course, remember about the counter that you have to reset it. Ok. And the concepts, we have a for-loop now, we have an if and an else...
125 S: Not that hard. And the instructions were very clear.
126
127 [00:12:09]
128
129 R: All right, great. Now I'm gonna give you, this is the question, can you order it? Put it in order, next to it, above it, or under it. We had the most difficult on top, where would you place this?
130 S: I guess this is more difficult because you have to do two things at the same time.
131 R: And which two things?
132 S: Finding out what the maximum is and see how many times it appears in the array.
133 [END DISCUSS TASK 81]
134 [00:12:42]
135 [BEGIN TASK 83B]
136 R: Ok, great. Here I have another one.
137 S: [silence for 15 seconds] So, we need to print the index, so first we need the index of the last rainy day, in, and if there's no rainy day, then we don't, we, we print an error message. Ehm... So, again we have to use a for-loop, and ehm, I guess we have to first find for the first, ehm, for the first, to see if there's a value in the array that's different than zero. And if all the values are zero, then we just print the error message. Ehm... I'm going to use the, to declare the, the count, the index or the for-loop in, outside the for-loop because if it reaches the end of the for-loop, ehm, or we can use a variable that's zero and then if it prints something, if we find a day that's, that had rain, we make it 1, and then at the end we can use an if, an if-statement to ask if it's zero, and then we print an error message. If it's not zero, we can print anything. You have a for, int i equals to zero, i smaller than rainValues... dot size... i++... If rainValues of i is different than zero... Ehm... Ok equals to true... In the... Now we print it on the screen... Ehm... of i... Ok, ehm, I have a question about this. If it's, if we, if the, if there's just one rainy day, do we print it twice?
138 R: Yes.
139 S: Ok, then I can use here "not ok", because we can just say that you go in the for-loop until you reach a variable, you reach a value that's not zero, and then you stop because now you find the first rainy day. And the, now we can use the for-loop in reverse order to find the last rainy day. Ehm... And we can make this variable false again, because we know that if we find the first variable that's not zero, then we should find something that's also not zero in this case, so ehm... rainValues.size in the... minus one... i is bigger or equal to zero... And eh... If, ok is, if not ok, then we system.out.println... Ehm... "There are no rainy days".
140 [END TASK 83B]
141 [00:17:57]
142
143 R: Ok. So at the end, you use the boolean variable, because first when you talked me through it, you said I'm gonna keep a variable, I'm gonna equal it to zero, and then I'll check if there's...
144 S: Ehm, yeah, I realized we should just use a boolean because you check whether it's different than zero or not.
145
146 [00:18:18]
147 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 83B]
148 R: Ok. All right, thank you. The questionnaire... There we go, the same questions. So the programme code, if you look at the code that you wrote, how about the algorithms, the algorithm, the code, is that more complex than what you've seen, have done?
150 S: I'll give it a 3, I think.
151 R: And why?
152 S: Because, now for the for-loop you use another boolean for stopping it, and we find the first, the first value that's not different than zero, and ehm... you also have...
153 R: Are you referring to the first boolean, or just for both of them? Yeah, yeah.
154 S: And ehm... Yeah, to see that you, if you, it doesn't matter if you use the same boolean because if you're, if you find a value the first time, and find a value the second time...
155 R: That you have to reset it.
156 S: Yeah.
157 R: Ok, and what else makes it more difficult?
158 S: I don't think anything makes it more complex.
159
160 [00:19:36]

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You: S6 WHILE harder/dispersed/error prone than FOR
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You: O4NEG recalls familiar plan
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You: O9 considers efficiency
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You: O9 considers efficiency
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You: S25 simultaneous tasks
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You: NOT O3 lacking terminate plan
Jan 10, 2024 1:55 PM • Edit

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You: O11 coding error but OK in interview
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You: S24 # tasks subsequent
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You: S23 vars with multiple roles / reuse
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162 R: All right. If you look at the concepts, which concepts do you see in the code, what have you been using that's extra compared to what we've done so far?

163 S: Well, I guess the boolean that stops the for-loop in case you find a variable that's not zero. So...

164 R: The "not ok" you mean?

165 S: Yes. So I guess it's not really that complex, but I'll give it a 1 because it's, yeah, it's not the same as those. And they were very clear, so.

166 R: Well, you had to ask a question about it. If the first rainy day's the same as the last, if there's only one value, do I print both?

167 S: Oh yeah.

168

169 R: Doesn't matter. Ehm, all right, here's the question, can you order it, we had the most difficult on top.

170 S: Ehm... I think it's... this one was most difficult.

171 R: Ok, so it's more difficult than the previous one, why?

172 S: Ehm... Well, because ehm, you just have to know when to stop the for-loop just so you print only one value, and not more than one value. And then for the second for-loop you need to kind of see that it doesn't matter if you change your boolean you'll still find the same value. If there's no other value, it's different than zero.

173

174 [END DISCUSS TASK 83b]

175 [00:21:16]

176 [BEGIN TASK 90]

177

178 R: Yeah, ok. Then... on to the next one.

179 S: [silence for 20 seconds] Ehm... Ok, so we can use a for-loop to go through the array, and then for each element we can either use another for-loop or a while-loop to count, to have an index that counts from zero to the value of each, of each value in this array. And then, each time we increase it we just print an asterisk. [silence for 14 seconds] Ehm... Int... i equals to zero... i smaller than rainValues.size... i++... Ehm... For int j equals to zero, j smaller than rainValues.of... should make it 1 because, ehm... j++... Ehm... system.out.print, eh... int, in the end of the... system.out.println.

180 [END TASK 90]

181 [00:23:30]

182 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 90]

183 R: Ok. Ehm, so you used a for-loop in a for-loop here? Ok. And you said first I can use a for, and then a for in a while?

184 S: Ehm, yeah. Either a for-loop in another for-loop or a while in a for-loop.

185 R: And why did you choose for a for in a for?

186 S: Ehm, I think it's just because for me it's easier to write the for-loops without mistakes because with the while there might, as I said here, you might do the index wrong and then it's, gives you errors, so...

187 R: Ok. And why did you use the, this for and not a for each?

188 S: Ehm... Well I've been working at this simple for, for longer and I'm used to it, even though probably the for each is more efficient, but I'm just, it's, I'm more used to it, because I work for more time with it.

189 R: Ok, because you called this the simple for, but it has more, has a lot more things than..

190 S: Simple for me, that it's, this [refers to for each] is more efficient I think, so, yeah, this one [for] I called it simple because it's just the simple one.

191 R: And this is what you've learned in class as well?

192 S: Ehm... In the imperative programming, yes, this is the only for-loop we learned.

193 R: Yeah. And you learned the while as well, you used a while as well? Ok, and which one did you learn first?

194 S: Ehm... first the while and then the for.

195

196 [00:25:06]

197

198 R: Ok. And then, when you learned the for, you thought it's easier because that makes less mistakes? Ok, perfect. Ehm, we go back to the survey question again... All right, if you look at the code that you wrote, how, the algorithm, how complex is the code?

199 S: It's a, not too complex because it's just two, it's a for-loop in another for-loop and then it's pretty easy of what you need to do inside the for-loop, so, yeah, that's why it's not that hard.

200 R: Ok.

201 S: The task covered are not too complex because again it's just two for-loops. And the instructions were clear.

202 R: Ok. If I would've asked you to do something that you don't only have to print the stars but you have to print the stars and something else, would that have made it a lot harder? If inside the for-loop, you have to do things, extra things?

203 S: Ehm... Well, I don't think so, because, well, it depends what it is, but if it's something that's just for each element you have to do something, then it shouldn't be too hard.

204 R: Ok, and if I would've asked you to do this and then afterwards something else, like print the maximum? would that have made it much harder?

205 S: Ehm, no.

206

207 [00:26:24]

208

209 R: Ok. All right, can you order it again?

210 S: [silence for 10 seconds]

211 R: Ok, and where did you put it now?

212 S: Under the for each-loop. just because I, it's probably not the good reasoning but that's how I think what I did it, because here you have to write more code and you have to be careful about the code you write, and this was just two for-loops in just like, four lines, and this is, ehm, oh, actually I should have put this lower, sorry...

213 R: No, that's ok. So you're saying now it's easier than...

214 S: Yeah, it's easier than all what we had so far.

215 R: Ok, so it's also easier than one for-loop?

216 S: Yeah.

217 R: with an if inside of it, because...

218 S: Yeah, because here you just have to print something, here you also have to check for values and count for it, so.

219 R: So you're saying printing is easier.

220 S: Yeah, because you just have to print something for each value, it's not...

221 R: Yeah. But printing, it's an act, it's a function call. You're calling a function, but...

222 S: Yeah, true, but...

223 R: Do you realize that when you print, or you're just like, this is some kind of statement?

224 S: Ehm, no, yeah, I know it's a function...

225 R: I know you know it, but do you real-, are you thinking about that this is a function, or are you just like, ok this is a line, or something...

226 S: Oh, ehm... Well, sometimes, maybe sometimes, but most of the times I know it works as putting something on the screen.

227 R: Yeah, so you can use it, can you use it without knowing that it's a function with parameters and you know, without thinking about that code?

228 S: Oh, ehm... Yeah, without parameters it won't work but it's just that I, it kinda got, because I use it so much, it kinda got into a reflex to put it, so...

229 R: Ok, so that's what makes, even though it's a function call, which people find pretty, some students find difficult to learn, even though it's a function call you still find it easier than an element. Ok. would it have been different if it had been a function call to another piece of code? Like, when you have to read that code?

230 S: Ehm... Not really. I mean, at the beginning, of the OOP course probably because I wasn't used to do all the classes and getters and setters, but now it shouldn't be a problem, I think.

231 [END DISCUSS TASK 90]

232 [00:29:04]

233

234 R: Good, all right. Excellent, thank you. Let's see... The last one.

235 [00:29:34]

236 [BEGIN TASK 88]

237 R: I wanna explain something, there's some code, there's the explanation and if you go a little bit lower, I gave two pieces of code that you can cut and paste. You can choose if you wanna use an array or an arraylist and you can just copy-paste it. You have to scroll down to see that.

238 S: Ok [silence for 25 seconds] Ok Ehm... I'm not really sure that all the [matters?] all that's predefined, but I'll try

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You: S23 vars with multiple roles / re-use
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You: S4 FOREACH least practiced
Jan 10, 2024 2:01 PM • Edit
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You: S1 construct familiarity
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You: O9 considers efficiency
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You: S1 construct familiarity
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You: S9 nested loops easy
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You: S18 nested conditional hard (harder than nested loop)
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You: S14 (novel) algorithm explicit thought/hard
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You: S18 nested conditional hard (harder than nested loop)
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You: S1 construct familiarity
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230 S: Ok, [silence for 23 seconds] Ok, Ehm... I'm not really sure that with the [unclear], but that's preferred, but I'll try
this because I just want to see if I remember correctly. If not, I'll use it the normal way...

239 R: Ok, because the other, this one you're familiar with and you know, ok, yeah. And why would you rather do an ArrayList?
240 S: Ehm... if I remember correctly, I think it's more efficient, because it's a list and not just a normal array. So the
list are usually work efficient and not more arrays, so... ehm... so... [silence for 15 seconds]

241
242 [00:31:00]
243
244 R: What are you gonna do?
245 S: Ehm... guess I use the for-loop for this as well. Ehm... can I assume that they have the same amount of...
246 R: Length? Yes, yes. Length is the same.
247 S: Ok. Oh, oops, didn't see that.
248 R: Doesn't matter, it's a good question.
249 S: Ehm... int i equals to zero... i smaller than... go to rainValue.size... i++... ehm... So, ehm... rainValuesMerged... I
know for adding something it should be add, but, and I think for getting the value, rainValues1.get(i), I think. And now
just do the same thing for the second array. Ehm... Yeah. Oh, print it, ok print, so, ehm... That's the for-loop, int i
equals to zero, i is smaller or equal than rainValuesmerged.size... i++... Ehm... system.out.print... print...
rainValuesMerged, dot get... i... Ehm... not sure if this works in print, but just to add a space I guess.

250
251 [00:33:52]
252
253 R: Oh, so then it's... yeah, so it's printed the... Ok. Great, ehm... If you look at the program code...
254 S: Yeah, I'd say for me at least, because I'm still not, I always had to look back to see what methods the list have,
between four and five but I'll put 5 because I had to look all the time for the methods that they have. Ehm... They are
probably, I'll say 4, like the concepts, because in the imperative programming we didn't do this but here it's like a very
new concept on how you use lists in OP. Like in object-oriented programming. So yeah, I'll just say 4.

255 R: Because how did you use lists in imperative programming?
256 S: We didn't really list it.
257 R: Oh, you didn't do lists at all? Ok, and so the methods you're saying, the add and the get, that makes it...?
258 S: Yeah, it's just that I know that at least the list interface has this method, but I'm not sure if the ArrayList has
this, but I think it does. So, yeah I always have to check if this method actually work or not. And the instructions were
clear, just because there wasn't, I didn't read fully to the end of the task.

259 R: Yeah, and afterward halfway you were like, oh yeah, I still have to print it. Did you forget that, or did you read half
the question...?
260 S: I usually read the whole problem, but I don't always remember everything and then I look back to see if I missed
something or not.

261 [00:33:50]
262 [END TASK 88]
263 [00:35:40]
264 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 88]
265 R: Ok, good. All right, that was it. Thank you. No, actually I have one step, this one. We have to put that in the right
place.
266 S: Ok, yeah I'll put it as the hardest one because of the ArrayList, yeah.
267 R: Ok. I'm going to take a picture of that.
268 [END DISCUSS TASK 88]
269 [00:36:08]
270
271 S: I'm going to mention that, I don't know, maybe as background or something, it's just that in high school I did four
years of computer science. So...
272 R: Ok, and what languages did you do?
273 S: We learned C++ and we learned a lot of algorithms, like we did, like what we did in imperative programming we did,
[methodsearch?], [differsearch?]. Yeah we did the graphs, a lot of programmes we did graphs, we did lists as well,
dynamic programming.
274 R: Wow, and this was in...
275 S: Romania.
276 R: Wow, that's impressive.
277 S: Yeah so it does, because I had in, what I would say is that I think that really helped me, because we really, we had
more time to focus on each like, especially recursion, time to focus on like, for, I think we did it one full year, just
recursion.
278 R: Wow, in Holland we barely, only mention it in high school.
279 S: Yeah, I think that's why it was really helpful for what we did in this courses.
280 R: Yeah, I can imagine that. Ok.
281
282 [hands out gift voucher]
283

You: O9 considers efficiency
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Resolve Reply

You: S1 construct familiarity
Jan 10, 2024 2:13 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O10 minor forget&recall
Jan 10, 2024 2:15 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply